

UZBEKISTAN'S LARGE-SCALE REFORMS WITH THE UNITED STATES OF AMERICA.

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Abstract: One of the priority goals of the Republic of Uzbekistan is to establish friendship, bilateral strategic partnership and comprehensive relations with the countries of the world. Similarly, with the United States of America. Uzbekistan and the USA are members of a number of international organizations, including the United Nations, the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe, the International Monetary Fund and the World Bank. Uzbekistan is a member of the "Cooperation for Peace" organization of the North Atlantic Treaty Organization and an observer of the World Trade Organization, and is currently preparing to join it.

Key words: Central Asia, regional contributions, trade and economic exchange, support for democratization

The Republic of Uzbekistan started to establish diplomatic relations with the USA in 1992 after independence from the Soviet Union. Since then, the United States and Uzbekistan have developed a wide-ranging relationship, cooperating in areas such as border and regional security programs, economic relations, political and civil society issues, and English language education. Uzbekistan is important to US interests in ensuring stability, prosperity, and security in the Central Asian region. Regional threats include illegal drugs, human trafficking, terrorism and violent extremism. Uzbekistan is a key partner in providing international humanitarian aid to Afghanistan and continues to support the country through electricity, economic aid and infrastructure development.

The United States of America continued close relations with Uzbekistan after its independence. After the September 2001 terrorist attacks in the United States, Uzbekistan offered overflight and basing rights to US and coalition forces. However, following US criticism of the Karimov government's violent suppression of unrest in southern Andijan and other actions in 2005, basic US rights in Karshi-Khanabad were suspended. Since then, the United States has been trying to improve ties, particularly in support of operations in Afghanistan. In 2009, Uzbekistan began to participate in the Northern Distribution Network of land, sea and air transit routes from Europe through Eurasia for the entry and exit of US and NATO military cargo to Afghanistan.

Total U.S. aid to Uzbekistan in fiscal years 1992-2010 was \$971.36 million (all agencies and programs). About two-fifths of this aid is budgeted for countering weapons of mass destruction (including aid for comprehensive threat reduction), foreign military financing, counternarcotics, cooperation for peace, and anti-crime aid. Food, health and other social security and humanitarian aid accounted for almost a quarter, and democratization aid for a fifth. Budget support totaled \$11.3 million in fiscal year 2011 and \$16.7 million in fiscal year 2012, and the administration requested \$11.6 million for fiscal year 2014 (these latter

amounts include the Congressional Foreign Operations Budget includes listed foreign aid and excludes funds from the Department of Defense and Energy; country data (FY 2013 not yet available).

As we all know, the USA is the leader on earth in many fields. For example, at the end of 2017, the gross labor product exceeded 18 trillion dollars. In turn, Uzbekistan, located in the heart of Central Asia, bordering all the countries of the region and Afghanistan, has a consistently growing economy and access to a large consumer market and, of course, to the markets of all neighboring countries. . The republic, which has a cheap but highly qualified labor force and rapidly developing infrastructure, is a very promising investment partner.

Therefore, Tashkent and Washington give priority to strengthening trade and economic exchanges in their mutual relations. Since 1993, the regime of creating the most favorable conditions in trade relations has been in effect. The United States - Central Asia Trade and Investment Framework Agreement (TIFA), signed in 2006, also contributes to the development of practical relations.

In September 2017, within the framework of the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly in New York, the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev held a number of productive meetings with representatives of the US business circles, and also participated in the Uzbekistan-US business forum with the participation of more than a hundred leading American companies. At the end of the event, a large set of documents with a total value of 2.6 billion US dollars was signed with US companies, covering the fields of oil and gas and petrochemicals, mechanical engineering, electrotechnical industry and civil aviation. In February 2017, a similar business forum was held in Tashkent.

The significant opportunities of Uzbekistan in the recreation industry and the favorable conditions created for tourism business in our republic attracted the attention of the "Hyatt" corporation. Today, the luxurious Hyatt Regency Tashkent hotel adorns the capital of Uzbekistan. Currently, the company plans to open a chain of hotels in Bukhara, Khiva and other cities. Another large corporation - "Hilton" is also planning to enter the market of Uzbekistan.

It is particularly significant that the business environment in our republic, which has recently taken systematic measures to liberalize the currency policy, simplify the tax regime, create additional convenience and benefits for investors, attracts the attention of leading firms and companies of the USA.

There is no doubt that the current level of trade and economic relations between Uzbekistan and the United States does not fully meet the potential and aspirations of the parties. A number of specific measures are envisaged in the priorities for the development of the foreign political and economic cooperation of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the main foreign partners in the medium-term perspective, recently approved by the Decree of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev.

In particular, it is envisaged to expand cooperation with the United States in the issues of modernization of the Uzbek economy, training of personnel and development of human capital, including the participation of the republic in the World Trade Organization by attracting the investment and advisory support of the United States.

How important is all of this in view of the plans of Uzbekistan to qualitatively update the national economic system in order to ensure the well-being of our people and future

generations, rapid and stable development of industries, especially the development of the economy on the basis of high technologies it is obvious that he has.

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